

GRETIL: Integrating Indology's Largest Corpus into the TextGrid Repository (Preprint)

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- Abstract English: GRETIL is a digital corpus of primary texts in mostly premodern Indian languages, actively maintained from 2001 to 2020. To ensure long-term preservation, it was migrated to the Text Grid Repository, converting the files to TEI and enriching the metadata with GND and Basic Classification classes, among other aspects. A new facet-based system replaced the old folder structure, enabling more flexible and precise queries. Complete corpus ZIP files were transferred to the DARIAH-DE Repository for cumulative downloads, while associated secondary literature was moved to the SUB's eDoc server. This migration serves as a model for future projects dealing with heterogeneous data and standardization needs.
- Abstract German: GRETIL ist ein digitales Korpus von Primärtexten in überwiegend vormodernen indischen Sprachen, das von 2001 bis 2020 aktiv gepflegt wurde. Um die langfristige Erhaltung zu gewährleisten, wurde es in das Text Grid Repository migriert, wobei die Dateien unter anderem in TEI konvertiert und die Metadaten mit GND- und Basisklassifikation-Klassen angereichert wurden. Ein neues facettenbasiertes System ersetzte die alte Ordnerstruktur und ermöglicht flexiblere und präzisere Abfragen. Die ZIP-Dateien des vollständigen Korpus wurden für kumulative Downloads in das DARIAH-DE Repository übertragen, während die zugehörige Sekundärliteratur auf den eDoc Server der SUB verlagert wurde. Diese Migration dient als Modell für zukünftige Projekte, die sich mit heterogenen Daten und Standardisierungsanforderungen befassen.

1. Introduction

This paper presents an overview of the final developments of the Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL), which, over the course of almost twenty years, developed into one of the largest corpora of machine-readable texts in the field of Indology. It outlines the historical development of the project up to 2020 and describes the subsequent phase of integration into repositories such as the TextGrid Repository, during 2024 and 2025.

2. GRETIL: Characteristics and History

GRETIL was conceived in 2001 by Reinhold Grünendahl (1950–2024), who served as librarian for South and Southeast Asian Philologies at the State and University Library (SUB) Göttingen. In line with institutional directives to expand digital library services, and in response to reductions in the acquisition budget for printed materials, he increasingly focused on the collection and curation of digital texts. The original announcement circulated via the Indology mailing list on November 2001 read:

“GRETIL is intended as a cumulative register of the numerous download sites for electronic texts in Indian languages. It registers only e-texts that are freely available for scholarly purposes and can be employed for word search etc. in a standard word processing programme.”¹

Initially, GRETIL functioned partly as a register of hyperlinks to external platforms hosting electronic texts, while also hosting locally maintained versions of selected texts. A central technical characteristic of the early platform (Figure 1) was the use of custom character encodings, not to be mistaken for with text encoding schemes. While Unicode gradually became more common for Sanskrit and related languages in the early 2000s, the majority of web-based resources at the time relied on legacy encodings rendered through custom fonts that overwrote standard code points in order to display Indic glyphs. Grünendahl and early contributors developed extensive toolkits for searching, normalising, and converting between these encodings.

Originally, GRETIL distributed texts exclusively in REE and CSX,² both of which were ultimately based on the CP437 code page that had been in use since the early 1980s. Approximately two years after the project’s inception, UTF-8 encoding with non-XML HTML markup was introduced as an additional distribution format.

As many of the original source websites from which texts had been harvested were discontinued, GRETIL increasingly assumed a preservation-oriented role. In several cases, it remained the only publicly accessible source for particular texts. This development strengthened its standing within the philological community and led to a growing number of scholars contributing research data in the form of primary texts. Over time, the conversion of these contributions into multiple encoding formats became a stable service, normalising texts at the level of character encoding and organising them into language-specific sub-corpora.

¹ <<https://wujastyk.github.io/INDOLOGY-forum-data/raw-data/2001/11-00007.txt>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

² Cf. the snapshot of the website as of April 2002: “In a first step, the source files have been converted to an encoding devised sometime in the 1980’s by the late Ronald E. Emmerick [...] for WordPerfect 5.1 DOS and related utility programmes [...]. In memory of its esteemed author this encoding is here referred to as ‘REE’. [...] In addition, all files in REE encoding were then converted to CSX (Classical Sanskrit Extended) encoding.” <https://web.archive.org/web/20020415134234/http://www.sub.uni-goettingen.de/ebene_1/fiindolo/gret_ree.htm#Intro> (accessed 2025-12-08).

Where source files contained annotations, GRETIL commonly provided parallel versions of the texts, both with and without annotation layers, across all supported encodings. Access to the material was offered through a static web interface that provided direct links to human-readable and downloadable files, resembling the browsing logic of a traditional library catalogue.

This resulted in a vast heterogeneity of the metadata available for these texts: For some, nothing more than the domain the original file was hosted at could be specified. Most gave reference to its printed source, while some others were de-facto digital editions. In lieu of licensing, Grünendahl originally delegated the possibilities for re-use to the diligence of its users, which made it difficult to cite the resource as such. Consequently, the factual distribution of GRETILs corpus should be expected not to be limited to projects crediting it directly. After 2016 most of the texts could be provided with Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike licences (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0). Among known re-use cases are multiple backup copies of the corpus on GitHub³ as well as platforms that (re-)render the corpus in Indian scripts.⁴ It has been prominently used for the biggest natural language processing (NLP) projects (Nehrdich et al. 2024, p. 13744)⁵ in Indology alongside the data of roughly contemporaneous platforms that are more uniform by their focus on linguistic annotation,⁶ certain religious affiliations⁷ or technical standards,⁸ but were at the time smaller in scale.

³ Cf. <<https://github.com/INDOLOGY/GRETIL-mirror>> (accessed 2026-04-30).

⁴ Cf. <<https://www.sanskritworld.in/>> (accessed 2026-04-30).

⁵ This work lays groundwork for the landmark meta-platform Dharmamitra <<https://dharmamitra.org/>> (accessed 2026-04-30). Also cf. Oliver Hellwigs *Digital Corpus of Sanskrit* (DCS) <<http://www.sanskrit-linguistics.org/dcs/>> (accessed 2026-04-30).

⁶ Cf. <<https://titus.uni-frankfurt.de/>> (accessed 2026-04-30).

⁷ Cf. <<https://muktabodha.org/digital-library/>> and <<https://www.dsbcproject.org/>> (both accessed 2026-04-30).

⁸ Cf. <<https://github.com/sarit/SARIT-corpus>> (accessed 2026-04-30).

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GRETIL - Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages
and related Indological materials from Central and Southeast Asia

Last Update: 10.09.2020

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Introduction

The Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL) is a resource platform providing standardized machine-readable texts in Indian languages that have been contributed by various individuals and institutions. GRETIL was originally intended as a cumulative register of the numerous download sites for electronic texts but has shifted its focus to securing and documenting the efforts to encode these texts. It does so by providing the contributions of varying sources and quality in an appropriately normalized way, with the minimum requirement being that full text search for each language is possible across the whole corpus without any additional conversion.

Please consider contributing! Whether you are preparing a critical edition, a diplomatic transliteration of a manuscript, or typing a printed edition for your research, we are always looking for new additions. You can contribute texts in any format you are working with or have been working with in the past; feel free to [contact us](#) and consult with us if you need any help or have any questions regarding GRETIL.

In the list below, the structure of the entries is as follows:

author / title (input by ...)

- link to download site of source file
- converted and normalized files
- link to sites providing the respective text / file in other formats / encodings

Please note that we are currently in the process of converting our corpus to adhere to the standards proposed by the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI); we are using this opportunity to make this resource platform more versatile and transparent for scholars around the world while maintaining the simplicity of the original concept as a register. This also means simplifying and streamlining the formats we are offering. With an [update history](#) since 2001 some features inevitably have become out-of-date. Thus the CSX- and REE-formats based on non-Unicode (CP437) character encoding are deprecated and will be discontinued. You can still access the respective files provided up until the update of June 28th, 2019 [here](#).

Cumulative Download

- [Download All Sanskrit Texts](#)
- [Download All Pali Texts](#)
- [Download All Prakrit Texts](#)
- [Download All Texts in NIA Languages](#)
- [Download All Texts in Dravidian Languages](#)
- [Download All Texts in Old Javanese](#)
- [Download All Texts in Tibetan](#)
- [Download All Secondary Resources](#)

Sanskrit

Veda

See also [Bloomfield: A Vedic Concordance](#)

Samhita

Introduction

Cumulative Download

E-texts in Sanskrit

Veda

Epics

Purana

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Poetry

Sastra

Material from Indonesia

Later works

E-texts in Pali

Tipitaka

Paracanonical Texts

E-texts in Prakrit

E-texts in New Indo-Aryan Languages

E-texts in Dravidian Languages

Tamil

Malayalam

Manipravalam

E-Texts in Old Javanese

E-Texts in Tibetan

Secondary Resources

GRETIL e-library

Update History

Figure 1: Previous GRETIL platform,⁹ as it was by the end of 2025

The project was thus strongly shaped by Grünendahl's understanding of digital librarianship. This orientation was also reflected in an additional strand of activity: the digitisation, scanning, and optical character recognition of (mostly) out-of-copyright primary and secondary literature in Indology. These materials were often produced in response to personal requests by colleagues from all over the world and were subsequently made publicly accessible through both the library's OPAC (Figure 3) and the GRETIL website when thematically appropriate.

⁹ <<https://gretil.sub.uni-goettingen.de/>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

The GRETIL e-library is a collection of electronic editions of books and articles on Indological and related subjects. The focus is on older standard works, along with writings relevant to the history of indology and related fields (Wissenschaftsgeschichte).

[GRETIL e-library OPAC](#) | Related websites: [GRETIL e-texts](#) | [Göttingen Indological Resources](#) | [SUB Göttingen Homepage](#)

Figure 2: Platform of the GRETIL e-library,¹⁰ as it was by the end of 2025

In 2016, responsibility for the project was transferred to a new, part-time position dedicated exclusively to GRETIL, a position occupied by Maximilian Mehner. At that time, the project comprised three main components:

1. The normalisation and integration of contributed research data into the existing corpus of machine-readable texts, the main GRETIL collection,
2. the maintenance of the collection of PDF facsimiles, known as the GRETIL e-library,
3. and the maintenance of the retrieval platforms for both the e-text corpus and the PDF library, i.e. the GRETIL website and OPAC integration.

¹⁰ <https://gretil.sub.uni-goettingen.de/gr_elib.htm> (accessed 2025-12-08).

Figure 3: GRETEL's OPAC,¹¹ part of the library catalogue, as it was by the end of 2025

The technical infrastructure inherited at that point was highly idiosyncratic. Core workflows were implemented using WordPerfect 5.2 on a legacy Windows XP system that had long been classified as a security risk by institutional IT services. The normalisation and integration of e-texts relied on more than twenty custom macros. Unicode output could only be generated indirectly by reloading CSX-encoded files into a slightly newer version of WordPerfect and exporting them via a custom printer driver.

In response to these constraints, the modernisation strategy focused on discontinuing the REE and CSX formats and introducing a single-source publishing model based on TEI-XML, from which all output formats were generated automatically using XSLT transformations. As part of this process, portions of the existing corpus were migrated from the UTF-8 encoded HTML versions to TEI-conformant XML.

This restructuring substantially reduced the manual effort required for encoding conversions and file generation. However, the TEI markup itself remained a labour-intensive, partly manual task. Due to limited project duration and resources, this technical overhaul could only be applied to a portion of the existing corpus.

By the time the last person working on the project left in 2020, GRETEL lacked a comprehensive long-term institutional or technical strategy. The corpus remained heterogeneous with respect to character encodings, file formats, and the completeness and consistency of metadata. Discovery and access were still largely dependent on a static, catalogue-like web interface, without advanced features for corpus overview, faceted browsing, or structured querying.

¹¹ <<https://opac.sub.uni-goettingen.de/DB=1.20/LNG=EN/>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

3. The Need for a Sustainable Plan for GRETIL

After that point, members of the research community expressed concern about data loss and the need for a long-term plan. In fact, GRETIL's data had begun to be forked in several GitHub repositories and associated platforms, such as Zenodo.

In 2022, Text+ was approved as part of the German Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) initiative. The consortia in this initiative are organised by subject, with the aim of improving the integration of existing resources to enhance the FAIR status of research data. Text+ is the consortium for textual data (Hinrichs et al. 2022). As part of Text+'s application process, a call for user stories was launched, inviting researchers to suggest ideas for the consortium to consider. One of these user stories (Buchholz 2022) proposed integrating the GRETIL files into the TextGrid Repository (TGR) (Neuroth et al. 2015; Calvo Tello et al. 2023).

In parallel with this process, discussions at the library addressed the possibility of bringing the project to an end, while ensuring long-term accessibility of the data. José Calvo Tello supervised the project on the technical side and David Herting contributed the Indological expertise. The suggestion of integrating the GRETIL data into the TGR was discussed with Grünendahl, who considered it a good possibility but expressed concerns about potential data and functionality loss. One benefit was that the TGR is backed not only by the SUB Library, but also by the GWDG (Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen, or Association for Scientific Data Processing Göttingen in English), both institutions being part of several NFDI consortia.

The migration work started in 2024. Sadly, this work began only weeks after Grünendahl's death. His presence was missed throughout this phase of the project, as was his invaluable input on the data, the project's history and the decision-making process. Throughout our work, we have endeavoured to honour his original vision.

4. FAIR-ification: Validation, Metadata Enrichment and Homogenisation

Two main sections of GRETIL data were identified:

1. The main GRETIL collection, which is a compilation of primary literature in various languages (primarily Sanskrit) in TEI and HTML format.
2. The GRETIL e-library collection, which is a compilation of secondary literature from the past two centuries, primarily in PDF format.

Although we could have imported the data as it was into a repository, we decided that it would be beneficial to invest some time in improving the data quality. These improvements can be grouped into two general tasks: data homogenisation and metadata enrichment.

In relation to the homogenisation, we converted all the files into TEI. While the majority of the Sanskrit texts (779 files) and two Tibetan texts were already in that format, the other language texts (447 files) had been encoded in a simple non-XML HTML format. First, we decided to apply the same template that was used for the TEI header of the Sanskrit texts. Although we considered improving the TEI encoding manually, this was not possible within the scope of the import process. Instead, we decided to use only TEI `<ab>` elements within

the `<text>` element.¹² The metadata of these files was copied into the TEI header as a legacy header, after which the metadata was manually inserted into individual TEI elements.

Second, we validated all TEI files for well-formedness and against the TEI schema used by the project. Surprisingly, many TEI files already encoded did not pass these validation steps. The team then corrected a range of errors manually.

For the migration, some metadata fields were required to be encoded in accordance with standards and controlled vocabularies. Previously, many of GRETIL's metadata was only implicitly present in the structure of the projects, e. g. in the names of folders. In order to maintain backwards compatibility, we decided to keep the previous metadata structure of files that were already encoded in TEI as much as possible, only adding attributes and elements where necessary.

The most important metadata improvements (many of them shown now as facets in the repository) are:

- The languages are encoded following the ISO-code 393-3 (standard for the TGR).
- Names of authors and titles of works have been standardised according to the respective transcription schemes for Indian languages.
- We used the Basic Classification system to categorise the subject of the texts, already used in other projects in the TGR (Rißler-Pipka et al. 2023). This library classification system is widely used in German-speaking countries, being an open resource. We used it for encoding the language family and the subject of the text. This provides a clear overview of the subjects in the GRETIL collections, displayed as facets. The top categories are philosophy and literature, but others are also present such as law, astronomy, sexuality, or lexicology.
- The TGR requires a genre from a list of six options: *verse*, *prose*, *drama*, *non-fiction*, *reference work*, and *other*. We mapped the folders of the previous version of GRETIL to these values, often being the selected value *other*.
- The previous version of GRETIL used a folder system with more accurate terms for describing documents, such as *Veda*, *Samhita* and *Saiva*. In order to preserve as much metadata from the previous project and offer terms accepted by the research community, we used them but mapping them with the authority file system of the German-speaking libraries, the GND (Gemeinsame Normdatei or Integrated Authority File in English; Kett et al. 2022). The majority of the terms were already present, and for those that were not yet available, we suggested them to the GND agency within Text+. We also identified several duplicated terms in the GND and these were merged and corrected. In this way, we not only connected GRETIL with the GND, but also contributed to enrich and correct it.

¹² Several other options with more specific text elements were considered, especially for differentiating the basic characteristics of text, such as verses (`<l>`), prose paragraphs (`<p>`) and theatre with direct speech (`<sp>`). However, this would require manually controlling all documents and ensuring the accuracy of all elements within the `<text>` Element. We considered doing this, at least for a fraction of the corpus. Sadly, the economic and personal constraints of the project forced us to choose the simpler strategy of using `<ab>`.

- People involved in the project were also identified through the GND.

This enrichment process raises several questions regarding two components. The first was a section of the Pali collection commissioned by the Pali Text Society.¹³ The HTML encoding of this collection was notably more complex than that of the other HTML files from other collections of GRETIL. Converting these HTML files into simple TEI, as described above, seemed to downgrade these documents. Unfortunately, we were unable to gather the necessary resources for a conversion of proper quality. For this reason, we decided to import these files only as ZIP files into the DARIAH-DE Repository (see Section 5.2.).

The second component is a collection of Sanskrit dictionaries and encyclopaedias that had been encoded in TEI. The previous version of GRETIL linked to the Cologne Digital Sanskrit Lexicon¹⁴ as the source — a CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure) portal that is also part of Text+. The portal continued to work on these files and released several updates which were not included in the GRETIL version. This is why we decided not to update these files, but rather to simply reference the CLARIN portal.

5. Integration in Repositories

We considered which repository or repositories would be most beneficial for integrating the data. Several criteria were considered, such as their user-friendliness and the features offered by the different repositories for the different formats. As TEI played a central role in GRETIL, it was clear that the TGR would be involved in the integration process.

In order to take advantage of the benefits of different repositories, we decided to integrate different sections of data into different repositories, while offering links between them to help users find all the data in a user-friendly manner.

5.1. TextGrid Repository

GRETIL was imported into the TGR using the new publication workflow (Veentjer et al. 2025) and now is a project within the repository.¹⁵ Its landing page is currently the project's main page, containing a short description and links to other repositories.

¹³ <<https://palitextsociety.org/>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

¹⁴ <<https://www.sanskrit-lexicon.uni-koeln.de/>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

¹⁵ <<https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-2ba9cb1b-9602-202d-71ce-67e63a29de55>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

TextGrid Repository

Shelf 0 Deutsch

Search term [Content](#) [Documentation](#)

Advanced Search

Views

- List
- Gallery

Tools

- Search within this project
- Search within fulltext of this project

GRETEL

The Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETEL) is a resource platform providing standardized machine-readable texts in Indian languages that have been contributed by various individuals and institutions. [more...]

Aggregation 1–16 of 16 [Change display](#)

other files [+ Add to shelf](#)

Download

[more metadata](#)

Tibetan Collection [+ Add to shelf](#)

Download

Figure 4: Start of the landing page of GRETEL in the TGR

On the landing page, users can find a link to an overview of all the files within the project. Many of the metadata described in Section 4 are shown here as facets, with the quantification of files assigned to each facet displayed. Figure 5 shows a list of texts on the right and several facets on the left, such as author, GND entity, TGR genre and Basic Classification. These facets allow for a more flexible selection of documents than the previous folder structure.

<p>Project</p> <p>GRETIL 1171</p> <p>Author</p> <p>Nāgārjuna 25</p> <p>Dharmakīrti 13</p> <p>Tevaram Tirunanacampantar 12</p> <p>Abhinavagupta 11</p> <p>Iramalinka Cuvamikal 11</p> <p>▼ Show all</p> <p>GND Entity</p> <p>Sanskrit 641</p> <p>Śāstra 554</p> <p>Darśana 484</p> <p>Buddhist philosophy 363</p> <p>Dravidian languages 201</p> <p>▼ Show all</p> <p>Genre</p> <p>Other 970</p> <p>Verse 103</p> <p>Non-fiction 88</p> <p>Drama 10</p> <p>Basic Classification</p> <p>18.67 Sanskrit: Language and literature 850</p> <p>08.10 Non-Western Philosophy: General 486</p> <p>17.97 Texts by a single author 324</p>	<p>☒ GRETIL > tibetan > Buddhacarita 1-23 (Tibetan translation) > Buddhacarita 1-23 (Tibetan translation)</p> <p>▼ more metadata</p> <hr/> <p>Tshangs-dbyangs-rgya-mtsho</p> <p>mgul glu</p> <p>☒ GRETIL > tibetan > mgul glu > mgul glu</p> <p>▼ more metadata</p> <hr/> <p>Sūyagaḍa</p> <p>☒ GRETIL > prakrit > Sūyagaḍa > Sūyagaḍa</p> <p>▼ more metadata</p> <hr/> <p>Āyāraṃga</p> <p>☒ GRETIL > prakrit > Āyāraṃga > Āyāraṃga</p> <p>▼ more metadata</p> <hr/> <p>Haribhadra</p> <p>Dhuttakkhāṇa</p>
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Figure 5: List of results of XML files of GRETIL in the TGR¹⁶

In the TGR, projects organise their data into collections. We decided to keep the structure similar to that of the previous GRETIL structure, which was organised first by language, with a Tibetan Collection, a Prakrit Collection, etc. Due to its size, the Sanskrit folder is organised into several collections, i.e. Purana Collection, Vedāṅga Collection, Śāstra Collection, etc. In total, there are now 15 collections (plus an additional collection for other files, such as the XSLT transformation), which are also displayed as a facet with the number of files attached to each collection (Figure 6).

¹⁶ <<https://textgridrep.org/search/?query=&order=relevance&limit=20&mode=list&filter=format:text%2Fxml&filter=project.id%3ATGPR-2ba9cb1b-9602-202d-71ce-67e63a29de55>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

Figure 6: Bar plot showing the number of documents in each of GRETEL's collections in the TGR

The repository is designed to support a wide variety of use cases. These can be arranged along a spectrum ranging from close to distant reading. At one end of this spectrum, users may wish to read a single text in the browser only. The repository allows users to access data in HTML format, as well as other formats such as plain text or ZIP files. At the other end of the spectrum, users can download all the project's corpora via the repository's bulk download options. Furthermore, the Python library `tg-clients` (Hynek et al. 2024) enables access to all texts and metadata. We have prepared a Jupyter Notebook which shows users how to access GRETEL data through these libraries.¹⁷ In the middle of the spectrum, users can use the shelf option of the TGR, select the texts that they want to gather, create their own sub-corpus and then decide to export it in different formats. Some tools are connected to the repository, such as Voyant Tools or CLARIN Switchboard, with more currently under discussion.

¹⁷ <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/textplus/collections/explore_gretil/-/blob/main/exploring_gretil.ipynb?ref_type=heads> (accessed 2025-12-08).

```

In [89]: aggregator.text("textgrid:48v6w.0").text

Out [89]: 'kaīrāya-sayambhueva-kiu\ṅpaūmacariu\ṅṅamaḥa ṅava-kamala-komaḷa-maṅahara-vara-vahala-kanti-s

In [90]: re.findall(r".{20}dha[rm]m[aoeā].{20}", aggregator.text("textgrid:48v6w.0").text)

Out [90]: ['Pc_3,8.3} jāya dāya-dhamma-raṅga-raṅgaṅāyara $',
'vandeppiṇu dasaviha-dhamma-pālu $ puṇu pucchiu',
'aviṭor apatyam bhānudharmā. bhānudharmaṇo 'pat",
'āna-jampāna-dhaya $ dhammeṇa bhicca-raha-turay',
'āharaṇa-vilevaṇai $ dhammeṇa ṅiyāsaṇa-bhoṅgaṇai',
'alattai maṅaharaī $ dhammeṇa chuhā-paṅḍura-gha',
'ra pomāēvi dasaviha-dhammavālayam $ gaū tettah',
'2,11.7} ehu savvahū dhammahū parama-dhammu $ j',
'āya dhamma-jīnesara dhamma-dhara $ jāya santi-',
'-ṅandi supasiddhā $ dhamma-santi jahī ṅāṅa-sam',
'āvem tihī mi jaṅḅhī dhammajjaṇu $ kiu candaṅa-',
'c_32,14.9} pekkhahu dhamma-phalu $ caūraṅga-va',
'tava-saṅjama-ṅiyama-dhamma-bharēṅa $ āiya ṅiya',
'u "mahāvaya-dhārā $ dhamma-pāva-phalu kahahi b',
' karevi thuṅa $ "ho dhamma-viddhi siri-ṅamiya-',
'amalindindira $ dasadhammāṅuvekkha suṅē dasa-s',
'taēṅa suhu kevalu $ dhammeṅ hontaēṅa cintiya-p',
'11.4} saccavāi jiṅa-dhamma-vacchalo $ sayala-k',
'} maharisi-vindu va dhamma-parāyaṅu $ paṅkaṅa-',
'_71,11.20} samāṅgaṅadhammam pi devāhidevam $ j',
'5.6} ṅigguṅa jaī vi dhamma-paricattā $ te ji v',
' bhāmaṅḍalu maṅḍala-dhammapālu $ akkhohaṅi-das',
'_78,11.3} dayā-mūla-dhammo $ paṅaṅṅaṅṅa-kamm',
'dama damiya ṅa vi $ dhamma-kkiya ekka vi ṅa ki',
'jjajjunā dhāi-dhava-dhammaṅā $ tāla-hintāla-tā',
'_81,14.9} tuhū puṇu dhamma-vahiṅi haū bhāyaru"',
'hava-saēhī viṅāsiya-dhammahō $ savvu dosu ēu d',
'83,20.8} khama-dama-dhammāhamma-purāṅai $ jaga',
'umhahī bhaṅahu cāru dhammaddhaū $ ṅijjiya-paṅc',
'ya-jammē uppajjai $ dhammahō ṅavara tahi mi mo',
'5} dukkhu dukkhu so dhammahō laggaī $ aṅṅāṅiu ',
' sumareppiṇu $ jiṅa-dhammahō vi pahāu muṅeppiṅ',
' viṅāsa-karaṅu dāya-dhammahō $ kohu jē mūlu gh',
'tthahō vi piya-jiṅa-dhamma-rasa $ hosanti saṅa']

```

Query Corpus with XPath

Figure 7: Jupyter Notebook exploring GRETIL's corpus through Python libraries

The findability and accessibility of data in the TGR is reinforced by the fact that each file has a persistent identifier. This identifier can be used to retrieve the data in various ways, for example via the TGR APIs, through the browser, or using the Python library `tg-clients`. Furthermore, the collections of these projects also obtain a citation suggestion.¹⁸ As with the previous platform, all documents are being published under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike licence (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0), as mentioned on the landing page.

One advantage of using GRETIL in the TGR is that the repository's various services handle the transformation into different formats. After the feedback gathered on Indology mailing list,

¹⁸ <<https://textgridrep.org/browse/48v63.1?lang=en>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

it was decided that we would use in the TGR the same XSLT stylesheet¹⁹ from the previous version of GRETIL, with minor updates. Consequently, users who were familiar with the HTML version of the GRETIL portal will find that the new portal has essentially the same transformation.

5.2. DARIAH-DE Repository

The previous GRETIL platform organised the TEI and HTML files of the main GRETIL collection into eight ZIP files under the heading 'Cumulative Download'. These ZIP files were used extensively by many users who expressed their interest in keeping this option.

Although the TGR offers similar bulk download options, we decided to maintain these files as they were. However, the homogenisation and enrichment steps described in Section 4 are not present here.

Cumulative Downloads

The previous GRETIL portal offered cumulative downloads of all files from each language or group of languages in ZIP files. As this option was widely used, we want to continue offering it. The ZIP files are now stored in the DARIAH-DE Repository (DOI: 10.20375/0000-0016-C802-4) and can be easily downloaded via the following links:

- [Sanskrit texts](#)
- [Pali texts](#)
- [Prakrit texts](#)
- [Texts in New Indo-Aryan languages](#)
- [Texts in Dravidian languages](#)
- [Texts in Old Javanese](#)
- [Texts in Tibetan](#)
- [Secondary resources](#)

Please note that the texts in these cumulative ZIP files are exactly the same as in the previous GRETIL portal and do not include the above-described improvements.

Figure 8: Section of the landing page of GRETIL in the TGR with the information and links to the cumulative download files in the DARIAH-DE Repository²⁰

We decided to migrate these files into the DARIAH-DE Repository (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), which is a generic repository for the Humanities. We obtained direct links to each ZIP file from this repository, and these were integrated into the GRETIL landing page in the TGR. This means that users can access the files directly without having to navigate within the DARIAH-DE Repository (Figure 8).

5.3. GRETIL eLibrary and eDOCS

As mentioned in Section 2., the GRETIL eLibrary is a collection of secondary literature on Indology, the vast majority of which is in PDF format. We decided to integrate them into the SUB's eDocs Server, which focuses on the Göttingen campus.

¹⁹ <<https://textgridrep.org/browse/textgrid:49zvj>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

²⁰ <<https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-2ba9cb1b-9602-202d-71ce-67e63a29de55#cumulative-downloads>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

Previously, the files were available on a GRETIL ad hoc server. However, these files could be found²¹ not only through a specific OPAC (Figure 3), but also through the library's general catalogue and the K10plus union catalogue.²² We extracted data from the files at this source, such as title, year of publication, subject (through the Basic Classification system) and author information. In most cases, the author was linked to the GND, which held information about the author's year of death. This information was used to confirm whether the documents could be safely published in the repository without any legal issues. For documents where the author died less than 70 years ago, an embargo date was set. This means that all documents are on the server, but only those currently in the public domain are available, as is the case for 361 documents. Users only obtain the metadata for the other 44 documents. We would like to thank our colleagues Michael Ernst and Marianna Muehlhoelzer at the library for their support with these tasks.

The screenshot shows the GRETIL e-Library interface. At the top, there's a header with 'eDocsSUBGöttingen' and 'Einloggen'. Below that, a navigation bar contains 'Startseite / Publikationen des Göttingen Campus / GRETIL e-Library'. The main content area is titled 'GRETIL e-Library' and includes a section 'AUFLISTEN NACH' with buttons for 'Erscheinungsdatum', 'AutorIn', and 'Titel'. There's also a 'Volltextsuche:' section with a search input and a 'Los' button. The GRETIL logo is prominently displayed, followed by a descriptive paragraph about the collection. Below this, a 'Dokumente' section lists three items with their titles, authors, and years. A sidebar on the right contains a search bar, radio buttons for 'eDocs Suche' and 'In dieser Sammlung', and a 'Browsen' section with buttons for 'Gesamter Bestand', 'Bereiche & Sammlungen', 'Erscheinungsdatum', 'AutorIn', 'Titel', 'Diese Sammlung', and 'Entdecke'. The 'Entdecke' section shows a list of years and their corresponding document counts.

Figure 9: GRETIL e-library in the eDocs repository

The GRETIL eLibrary collection in eDocs²³ (Figure 9) offers several options for browsing the collection using metadata such as author, year of publication, language and subject.

6. The Future of GRETIL

Thanks to homogenisation, enrichment and integration into repositories, GRETIL's data is now part of the library's long-term plan to ensure access to research data. The library is

²¹ <<https://edocs.sub.uni-goettingen.de/handle/4/24050>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

²² All the documents part of the GRETIL e-Library can be found with the search "abl gretil" <https://gvk.k10plus.de/SET=5/TTL=1/CMD?MATCFILTER=N&MATCSET=N&ACT0=&IKT0=&TRM0=&ACT3=* &IKT3=8183&ACT=SRCHA&IKT=1016&SRT=YOP&TRM=abl+gretil&TRM3=>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

²³ <<https://edocs.sub.uni-goettingen.de/handle/4/24050>> (accessed 2025-12-08).

continuing to work on improvements to these repositories, which could also benefit GRETIL in the future.

From a content perspective, GRETIL is regarded by the SUB Göttingen as a closed project. At the time of writing, no institutional resources are available for the addition of new texts or for philological emendation of the existing material.

Nevertheless, several aspects of the corpus remain open to improvement through the involvement of the Indological community. Researchers can decide to improve the encoding or add new texts and publish them as new projects, for example for those sections of the corpus that were converted to TEI in bulk. The TGR portal provides information on the simple steps researchers can take to achieve this.²⁴ A specific technical case is represented by the Pali Text Society sub-corpus, for which a customised rendering had been implemented and whose continued maintenance would now require partial revision of the existing transformation routines. Projects interested in those tasks can contact the team behind the TGR.

We believe that GRETIL can be seen as a good example of one possible development of digital pioneers. The project originated as a highly personalized assemblage of digital solutions and benefited from an unusual degree of institutional continuity beyond standard time-limited project funding. A significant part of its attractiveness lay precisely in this continuity, enabled by sustained institutional backing and the preservation-oriented ethos of its founder. But even in those cases, projects might find an ending and the long-term structural challenges have become increasingly evident. By combining project-specific features with institutionalised, distributed, and interconnected resources that use standards, projects can increase their chances of enduring in an ever-changing digital reality.

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²⁴ <<https://textgridrep.org/docs/publication?lang=en>> (accessed 2026-05-08).

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